

SYNERGY EFFECTS IN POLYMER COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT NANOCARBONS

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ABSTRACT

The dielectric/electric properties of polyurethane composites filled with carbon nanotubes (CNT), onion-like carbon (OLC) and mixed OLC/CNT are compared across a wide frequency range from hertz to terahertz. The dielectric/electric properties of composites filled with OLC are very attractive and can be improved by addition of small amounts of CNTs due to a strong synergism between the two carbon allotropes. Moreover, in composites with mixed OLC/CNT inclusions, the value of the percolation threshold is lower than the value predicted by the excluded volume theory. In composites with mixed OLC/CNT inclusions, the dielectric permittivity and electrical conductivity increases due to a decrease in the average distance between nanocarbon clusters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, electrically percolative polymer-based composites with various nanocarbon inclusions are very popular due to their outstanding electric, electromagnetic, mechanical and thermal properties in comparison with the polymer matrix material [1]. Many investigations of such composites were performed within a narrow frequency range and at room temperature in order to find the percolation threshold (the minimum concentration of nanofillers at which composites are conductive) [2]. An important task is to obtain a low percolation threshold in order to preserve (or reach) optimal mechanical properties of polymers and to use a minimal concentration of expensive fillers. The lowest percolation threshold was observed in carbon nanotubes (CNT) composites due to their high aspect ratios [3]. However, CNT usually agglomerate within the polymer matrix because of the high Van der Waals force between CNT, and this leads to an increase of the percolation threshold. Therefore, the percolation threshold in the same polymer matrix and for the same CNT can vary significantly [3]. Moreover, the percolation threshold in other composites, for example, in carbon black (CB) composites, can also be very low [4]. Thus, investigations of composites with other less expensive inclusions are very promising.

Onion-like carbon (OLC), consisting of stable, defected, multishell fullerenes, exhibit high conductivity similar to CNTs [5]. The percolation threshold in OLC composites is strictly dependent on aggregate size, and it is lowest for composites with the smallest aggregate size [6]. Particularly, in OLC/Polyurethane composites with an average aggregate size of ~120 nm, the percolation threshold is 10 vol% [7]. Thus, the percolation threshold in OLC composites is lower than predicted by Monte-Carlo calculations ~ 31.2 vol% [8] and can be lowered with improved composite preparation procedures [9]. Moreover, the dielectric permittivity of OLC based composites is very high (more than 10^6 at low frequencies), and these composites are very attractive for various applications [7]. However, the percolation threshold in OLC based composites is still much higher in comparison with CNT composites.

Multiphase composites with several different fillers in the matrix are very interesting due to the potential synergism between the different components [10]. Often, the distribution of different fillers within the polymer matrix can be favourable, and electrical transport can occur in different fillers network together. When this occurs, the percolation threshold can decrease dramatically in comparison with single filler composites [10]. Also, when the synergy effect is observed, the electrical conductivity of hybrid composites is higher a simple sum of the conductivities of corresponding binary systems [11]. Many investigations of synergy effects were performed in CNT/CB composites, and a significant decrease in the percolation threshold, in comparison with CB composites, was observed [10-12]. Usually, this synergistic effect was investigated only at room temperature.

In this paper we compare the broadband dielectric/electric properties of composites filled with CNT, OLC and mixed CNT/OLC composites at temperatures starting from room down to 26 K. It was demonstrated that the dielectric and electrical properties with OLC inclusions can be substantially improved with the addition of CNT.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Polyurethane films with nano-additives were prepared using Clear Gloss MINWAX® Fast-Drying Polyurethane. Nano-additives included: multi-walled CNT (20 nm diameter, 5-10 micrometer length) purchased from Amorphous Carbon Materials, Inc. and OLC derived by vacuum annealing of detonation nanodiamonds (DND) [5-7]. Aggregates of DND consisting of 5 nm primary particles were heated in vacuum (10^{-4} Torr) at 1650 °C for 3 h, providing aggregates of OLC with aggregate sizes corresponding to the sizes of the starting DND fractions (approximately 100 nm). Stock suspensions of nano additives (~0.5-1.0% w/v) were prepared in an alcohol solvent and sonicated with a horn-based sonicator for 30 minutes. 7 g of polyurethane (PU) was heated at a hot-plate at 60°C under magnetic stirring. The alcohol based suspension containing the desired amount and type of the nano-additives was added dropwise to the polyurethane while maintaining stirring. After the alcohol suspension was combined with the PU, the alcohol was evaporated from the PU-nanoadditive mixture. The samples were then cast on a teflon substrate and cured at 40°C for 24 h. After curing, the samples were annealed at 180°C for 0.5 h in order to homogenize nanofiller distribution. In this paper, composites containing up to 2 wt% inclusions of CNTs, up to 7 wt% of OLC, and mixed CNT/OLC containing up to 7wt% of OLC and constant concentration of CNT - 0.5 wt% were investigated. Microstructural characterization of the composites was performed using the JEOL-7600F scanning electron microscope.

Complex dielectric permittivity was measured as a function of frequency and temperature using a HP4284A precision LCR meter in the frequency range from 20 Hz–1 MHz. For the low temperature measurements, a helium closed cycle cryostat was used. In the frequency range from 1 MHz – 3 GHz, dielectric measurements were performed using a vector network analyzer (Agilent 8714ET). In the microwave frequency range from 8 - 53 GHz, a home-made waveguide spectrometer was used. The method of a thin rod in the waveguide was used [13]. In the frequency range from 1 MHz to 53 GHz, the measurements accuracy was ~ 10%. Silver paste was used for creating the contacts. In the terahertz frequency range (from 100 GHz to 3 THz) a terahertz time domain spectrometer (Ekspla Ltd) based on a femtosecond laser was used for the measurements. The spectrometer is based on the femtosecond fiber laser (wavelength 1µm, pulse duration less than 150 fs) and a GaBiAs photoconductive terahertz emitter and detector. The complex effective permittivity was calculated according to the Fresnel equation. All measurement above 1 MHz were performed only at room temperature. The real part of the complex electrical conductivity (σ') was calculated as $\sigma' = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon''$, where ω is the angular frequency, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum, and ϵ'' is the imaginary part of complex effective permittivity.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scanning electron microscopy images of composites filled with various inclusions are presented in Fig. 1. All composites demonstrate good quality, with carbon inclusions being reasonably well dispersed. However, the best dispersion of particles is observed in mixed CNT/OLC composites.

Frequency dependence of the dielectric permittivity and electrical conductivity of mixed composites with 0.5 wt% of CNT and different concentrations of OLC and pure polyurethane (at room temperature) are presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Scanning electron microscopy images of composites filled with 2 wt% of CNT (top), 2 wt% of OLC (middle) and mixed 2 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT (bottom).

The value of the dielectric permittivity of pure polyurethane is very low (about 2), and it is almost frequency independent for all frequency ranges. At low frequencies, the AC electrical conductivity of pure polyurethane is very low (about 10^{-9} S/m), and no frequency independent conductivity plateau -

typical for DC conductivity - is observed. The dielectric/electric properties of composites filled with 2 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% CNT inclusions are similar to pure PU properties; however, the values of dielectric permittivity and electrical conductivity for composites filled with 5 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT are considerably higher (at low frequencies the value of dielectric permittivity is 100x higher, and the value of electrical conductivity is as high as 1 μ S/m) and a frequency independent DC conductivity plateau is observed in the conductivity spectra. Thus, the percolation threshold in mixed OLC/CNT composites is close to 5 wt% OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT. In contrast, for the composites with only 5 wt% of OLC $\epsilon' = 16$, $\sigma = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ S/m and for the composites with only 0.5 wt% CNT $\epsilon' = 4.5$, $\sigma = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ S/m at room temperature and frequency 129 Hz. Therefore, the synergy effect is clearly observed in the composite containing a mixture of 5 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT. The value of the percolation threshold in PU filled with OLC inclusions was obtained by fitting the concentration dependence of conductivity and dielectric permittivity at the same frequency and at room temperature by the power law (not shown); it is substantially higher – 7 wt%.

Figure 2: Room temperature frequency dependence of dielectric permittivity and electrical conductivity for composites with mixed CNT/OLC inclusions.

In composites filled with CNT inclusions, no electrical percolation was observed up to the highest available filler concentration (2 wt%), thus the percolation threshold is substantially higher than 2 wt%. According to the excluded volume theory, the mixed OLC/CNT composites should obey the following relation [14]:

$$\frac{m_{OLC}}{P_{c,OLC}} + \frac{m_{CNT}}{P_{c,CNT}} = 1, \quad (1)$$

where m_{OLC} and m_{CNT} is the mass fraction of OLC and CNTs, respectively, and $P_{c,OLC}$ and $P_{c,CNT}$ is the mass percolation threshold in composites filled with of OLC and CNTs, respectively. The synergy effect is observed in ternary composites where the percolation threshold occurs at the concentrations

lower than predicted by Eq. (1) and percolation threshold values of binary composites [14]. In our case, for composites with 5 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% inclusions, Eq. 1 transforms into the inequality:

$$\frac{5}{7} + \frac{0.5}{x} < 1,$$

where x is greater than 2. Thus, the percolation threshold in mixed OLC/CNT composites is lower than the value predicted by Eq. 1, and the synergy effect is evident.

At low temperatures, both the dielectric permittivity and the electrical conductivity decrease in CNT/OLC/PU composites (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Temperature dependence of dielectric permittivity and electrical conductivity for composites with 5 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT inclusions.

However, the most pronounced reduction occurs at temperatures below 100 K. A similar behaviour was observed in other CNT/OLC/PU and OLC/PU composites and is in good agreement with the data presented in literature for composites with nanocarbon inclusions [15]. For composites with low concentrations of inclusions (although still above percolation threshold), not only the DC conductivity changes upon cooling, but the shape of the conductivity spectra is also changed (Fig. 3). Therefore, conductivity spectra, $\sigma(\nu)$, were fitted with the Almond-West equation [16]

$$\sigma = \sigma_{DC} + A\omega^s, \quad (2)$$

where σ_{DC} is the DC conductivity and $A\omega^s$ is the AC conductivity. From this fit, it is possible to calculate the critical conductivity frequency (ω_{cr}) at which the value of frequency independent conductivity becomes higher than DC conductivity. The critical frequency of composites with 7 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT inclusions is higher than 1 MHz (Fig. 1) (our upper frequency limit in low temperature measurements); therefore, the critical frequency values were calculated only for composites with lower concentrations of inclusions. Obtained parameters are summarized in Fig. 5. The DC conductivity data fit well to the fluctuation induced tunneling model, as can be seen in Fig. 5 [17]:

$$\sigma_{dc} = \sigma_0 \exp(-T_1/(T+T_0)), \quad (3)$$

where T_1 represents the energy required for an electron to cross the insulator gap between the conductive particle aggregates, and T_0 is the temperature above which thermally activated conduction over the barriers begins to occur. The tunneling model is represented by eqs. (4) and (5) [17],

$$T_1 = wA\beta_0 / 8\pi k, \quad (4)$$

$$T_0 = 2T_1 / \pi\chi w, \quad (5)$$

where $\chi = (2mV_0)^{0.5} / h$ and $\beta_0 = 4V_0 / ew$, m and e are the electron mass and charge, respectively, V_0 is the potential barrier amplitude, w is the interparticle distance (gap width), and A is the area of capacitance formed by the junction.

Figure 4: Frequency dependence of electrical conductivity at different temperatures for composites with 5 wt% of OLC and 0.5 wt% of CNT inclusions.

Obtained parameters are listed in Table 1. From Eqs. (4) and (5) it follows that T_1/T_0 is proportional to the gap width w and the potential barrier V_0 amplitude. The best distribution of carbon inclusions is in OLC/CNT mixed composites (Fig. 1); thus, the interparticle distance is lowest in OLC/CNT mixed composites.

The critical frequency (ω_{cr}) is related with DC conductivity according to the Barton-Nakajima-Namikawa relation:

$$\sigma_{dc} = \Delta\epsilon\epsilon_0\omega_{cr}, \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta\epsilon$ is the dielectric strength. Thus, for the critical frequency, we have assumed similar temperature dependence as for DC conductivity:

$$\omega_{cr} = \omega_{cr0} \exp(-(T_1/(T+T_0))). \quad (7)$$

The best fit was obtained with the same parameters for critical frequency and DC conductivity (Table 1).

Figure 5: Temperature dependence of DC conductivity and critical frequency of composites with various nanocarbon inclusions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The dielectric/electric properties of CNT, OLC and mixed OCL/CNT polyurethane composites are presented across a wide frequency range from hertz to terahertz. The dielectric properties of composites with OLC inclusions are also very attractive and can be improved by addition of small amounts of CNTs due to the strong synergy effect. In composites with mixed OLC/CNT inclusions, the dielectric permittivity and the electrical conductivity increase due to the reduction of the average distance between nanocarbon clusters.

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